

THE IMPORTANCE OF MOSH AND LEGUMES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4935091>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st June 2021

Accepted: 05th June 2021

Online: 10th June 2021

KEY WORDS

transplant, mung, green manure, mineral fertilizer, hot climate, free nitrogen, endogenous bacteria, symbiosis.

ABSTRACT

Today, changes in the structure of crops require the introduction of intensive technologies for the production of high quality crops from leguminous crops. One such technology is to increase grain yields by replanting early-maturing moss varieties as a re-crop in vacant areas after harvesting cereals planted in irrigated areas.

The article discusses agricultural technologies for the cultivation of mosses.

The role and importance of the agrarian sector in ensuring the demand of people in the world for food is increasing day by day. In particular, it is one of the most important issues in our country, ensuring the population with agricultural products, increasing productivity and productivity, scientific achievements and introduction of modern approaches to the sphere, using the available resources and opportunities correctly.

In his address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020, the distinguished president of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized that the fastest factor in reducing poverty and increasing the incomes of the rural population is a

sharp increase in productivity and productivity in agriculture.

In this process, it was one of the main tasks to increase the income from each hectare of land to at least 5 thousand dollars on average, and it was determined that we should widely introduce to agriculture the latest advanced technologies, water-saving and biotechnologies, achievements in the field of seeds, science and innovation.

The harsh coastal arable cabin of the agrarian coast is also part of the reformatlar of amirisa. The Strategy for Action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 years, approved in accordance with the

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy for Action for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan," in the near and long term, the structural transformation and the consistent development of agricultural production will be deepened, further strengthening the food security of the country, increasing the production of environmentally friendly products, a sharp increase in export capacity.

In order to provide the population with food in the world on an area of more than one million hectares of irrigated land released annually from cereals, based on favorable soil and climatic conditions in the Republic, macaqueas, moss, soybeans, rice, tara, sesame, fruit and vegetable crops, potatoes and various vegetables are re-crops for 120-130 days.

Changing the structure of crops requires the implementation of intensive technologies for growing high-quality crops from bean-grain crops. One such technology is to plant morning wheat varieties and increase grain cultivation on vacated areas after harvesting crops planted in irrigated areas.

Currently, our country pays great attention to grain, shop, oilseeds, and sowing areas are expanding. There are great opportunities for the development of agriculture and the efficient use of land. Today, one of the main problems is the issue of protein, that is, meeting the need of mankind for protein. In solving this issue, fruit growing from shop crops is of great importance.

Under the conditions of the republic, 60-70 c/ha is grown from winter wheat, and

from oilseeds grown as re-sowing - 15-20 c/s, it is possible to bring the crop of grain grown during one season to 75-90 c/s. On the ground will be planted shop and grain crops for 135 million hectares. It ranks second in the world (about 25 million ha) after soybeans (about 74 million ha worldwide) in terms of sown area among bean and grain crops and ranks third (about 10 million ha in total in the world).

Mosha is the best siderate, which, when used as sulfur agitation, accumulates in the soil for 70 kg of dry matter. Moss is the best siderat on lands where corn, vegetables and other crops are planted. Mosha is one of the best crops before grain, technical crops and vegetables as a nitrogen collector. You can sow it in spring and summer. Mosh's water waters are not contaminated with surface location, grow rapidly, are able to maintain soil moisture with good soy and are a useful type of crops when cleaning from foreign weeds.

One of the factors limiting their development in agricultural plants is their lack of sufficient supply with nitrogen compounds. Such, that is, in conditions of nitrogen deficiency, plants are surrounded by molecular nitrogen, which makes up about 80% of the atmospheric air. Legumes-cereals have the property of accumulating nitrogen in themselves. Legumes-grain crops accumulate a large amount of organic matter on earth, thereby improving the nitrogen balance in farming, making some of them a form of hard-to-absorb phosphates. The roots of leguminous plants enrich the soil with nitrogen, depositing atmospheric nitrogen with the help of depleted bacteria at the ends. In general, legumes-grain crops contribute to the development of three main tasks in farming:

the issue of plant protein, the increase in grain production and the increase in soil fertility.

Here it is advisable to give another fact. On the soil there are a large number of microorganisms, that is, on one 1 g of soil there are millions or billions of bacteria. Compared to air and water, there are many bacteria on the soil. Soil is the main source from which microbes pass into air and water. According to the analysis, up to 3-5 tons of bacteria are contained in a tier of up to 25 cm deep land planted on 1 hectare. The spread of bacteria on the soil depends on the nature of the soil.

As it became known from scientific sources, during the growing season, 50-100 kg of biological nitrogen and organic substances were collected on the soil, which, together with increasing the natural productivity of the soil, produce healing grain rich in proteins and vitamins.

According to scientists, childbirth will be diverse and diverse. The more and the more they are in the plant root, the more biological nitrogen accumulates in the soil. Plants are mastered with 60-75% of produced nitrogen, and the remaining 25-40% is left in the soil with an organic substance with angiosis residues. Part will be lost during denitrification.

Also, according to the data, mainly fossilized bacteria of the plant root develop intensively before the flowering period. During the flowering period, the transition of hydrocarbons from leaves to roots weakens, carbohydrates are mobilized to bloom flowers and fruits, so after flowering, bacteria die, and nitrogen organic matter begins to accumulate in the soil. In addition,

the protein formed in the seed will consist of an average of 5-7% derivatives.

On hot hot weather days (32 °C), legumes experience difficulties in developing free nitrogen from the atmosphere, as a result of which there is a shortage of nitrogen in the plant.

On the experiments conducted by the researcher of Tashkent State Agrarian University S.T. Negmatova, the mosh varieties "Joy" are spent normally 400 thousand acres/ha at the expense of each hectare of land. (1.07) yield during cultivation was 19.3 c/ha, protein content in grain - 27.5%, with a delay in increasing the consumption of seeds (540 thousand units/ha) in early August (1.08), the yield of copper sowing was 14 c/ha, a decrease in protein content was observed (25%).

Mosh is a crop that improves soil fertility as a leguminous plant, increases crop productivity by exchanging, saves nitrogen fertilizer, provides the opportunity to increase protein accumulation per hectare. Mosh leaves 2,5-3,0 tons of Root and angular residues in the soil after itself during the entire vegetation period.

The scrotum plant is a sowing plant that improves soil yield, increases the productivity of exchange sowing, saves nitrogen fertilizers, and makes it possible to increase protein harvesting per hectare. Mosh leaves 2.5-3.0 tons of roots and angioses on the soil throughout the growing season.

Mosha is the most popular culture. For normal growth and development of plants, a high temperature is required. Seeds begin to wash at a temperature of 8-10 °C, but rapid and relative humidity of

the seeds is observed at an average temperature of 12-14 °C, during early planting, the seeds are tightened, part of the seeds can disperse.

In this regard, planting a cat as a re-seeding corresponds to its demand for heat and completely takes 3-4 days. For Mosh, optimal conditions will be created at a temperature of 18-22 °C. Jaziram and in the heat it blooms calmly, and the crop ends. In the period of shunting and flowering, it is advisable to heat 20-25 °C. Mosh sowing withstands a temperature of up to 45-47 degrees. Mosh fruits and older plants are very impressive from the cold, and the degree of cold can lead to its death. Mosha is able to withstand hot and night cooling, that is, sharp changes in the weather. A useful temperature set for high-speed moss varieties is 1800 °C, for orthopedic varieties - 2000 °C.

Depending on the demand for humidity, mesophyte is part of the plant group. Copper seeds are quickly drilled, this requires 90-92% water compared to the dry weight of the seeds. When moisture escapes from saline soil, it affects the development and productivity of vegetation. Flour

requires less water than other types of algae. 3-4 days after sowing, pasture may appear (in other types of lava, the field is visible 6-12 days after planting). Despite the fact that arable land has antipyretic heat resistance, in any case it is poorly developed on dry soil. Therefore, keeping the soil cool is a very important condition that affects the development and yield of water.

There can be no overwetting of the soil. Otherwise, seed fertilization is delayed, making it significantly unsuitable for storage. Even when it is used as a seed, it does not have a good effect.

Output. As a rule, when planted in copper corn, they are watered 4-5 times during the growth period, and planted to you - 2-3 times. With each irrigation, up to 600-800 m³ of water is drained per hectare. Midges cannot grow in arid conditions. In the period after flowering, moss increases the need for moisture, with moisture on agar less than 65%, the bottom is ground, yield decreases, biological nitrogen does not accumulate at the root. After the start of packaging of the lower magazines, watering stops.

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